

The Edomite Enigma

*An Investigation into the Oracles of Malachi and Amos
Against Edom and Their Influence on Paul's and James'
Edom Statements in Romans 9:13 and Acts 15:16-18*

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In a recent course for my Ph.D. in Biblical Studies, I was surprised as my professor took us through a chart of oracles by OT prophets against many nations. I was not surprised that the prophets of Israel and Judah spoke to the nations of the world. I had long known that sections of Isaiah, Jeremiah, Ezekiel, Amos, Zechariah, and others contained oracles to specific nations. Indeed, two small books are devoted to this – Obadiah (Edom) and Nahum (Assyria). But what surprised me in my professor’s presentation is this fact; more oracles are spoken about Edom than any other nation! More than Egypt? More than Babylon? Well, I have not counted the number of words and verses, and Jeremiah was quite longwinded in chapters 50-51 against Babylon, but it is true that most individual oracles are directed against Edom.

We may ask, “Why?” And although Scripture provides no answer, for it would not anticipate such a question from modern people who like to count and categorize, it does provide an indirect answer; the enmity between the brothers Jacob and Esau. Although Genesis 33 records some type of reconciliation, I still remember the words of my high school Bible teacher who pointed out to me that when Esau invited Jacob to accompany him back to his home after their happy reunion, Jacob said he would come and then went the other way! And the fragile reconciliation that occurred crumbled in the ensuing generations. When the Israelites wanted to travel through the land of Edom on their way to the promised land, the Edomites refused and threatened them (Numbers 20:14-21). That set the tone for hundreds of years of enmity between the two nations, often displayed with unspeakable acts of cruelty, and words of woe from prophets that surpassed, in number, the words against any other nation.

In the following pages, we will look at two of the oracles against Edom; Malachi 1:2-5 and Amos 9:11-12. The Amos oracle is noteworthy because of its use by James in the Jerusalem Council recorded in Acts 15. The Malachi oracle is noteworthy because of its use by Paul in his famous Romans 9 chapter and is a key piece in the Calvinistic Arminian debate.

The Lord said through Malachi, “Jacob I have loved, and Esau I have hated.” Paul quotes these words in his letter (Rom 9:13) to explain how the promised kingdom can be present when Israel largely has not believed in its Messiah. Calvinists have viewed these words as a clear example of God’s sovereign freedom to elect one to salvation and to bypass another. Bypassing is too soft a word. He loves and predestines one to salvation and hates and predestines another to eternal damnation. There it is in black and white, “Jacob I loved, and Esau I hated.” Those words, coupled with “So then He has mercy on whom He desires, and He hardens whom He desires” (Rom 9:18) should be enough to convince everyone of the points of Calvinism, well, at least of the “U” petal in the Calvinist T-U-L-I-P, Unconditional Election.

But I am unconvinced.

This paper is adapted from an assignment for my course requirements. My assignment was to pick two pericopes from OT minor prophets and exegete them. Because of my interest in the Calvinist-Arminian debate, I selected two that pertain to Esau/Edom; Malachi 1:2-5 and Amos 9:11-12. As I said, the Malachi oracle is the passage Paul quoted in Romans 9. Thus, it interested me to investigate it more fully. The Amos oracle is the passage James quoted at the Jerusalem Council, recorded in Acts 15, as the biblical basis for the mission to the Gentiles.

Wait! An oracle against Edom is the foundation for the Great Commission? Hmmm ... that's interesting.

It's time to do some textual spadework, to gain a fuller understanding of what Malachi, Amos, Paul, and James had in mind, and to see if what we learn has any bearing on what Augustine first advocated and what Luther, Calvin, and many other Reformers advanced in the theological world of Christendom. Were they correct, or did the struggles of their time misinform them and skew their understanding of the words written by apostles and prophets?

Malachi 1:2-5 – Edom on the Outside!

²“I have loved you,” says the LORD. “But you ask, ‘How have you loved us?’ “Was not Esau Jacob’s brother?” declares the LORD. “Yet I have loved Jacob, ³but Esau I have hated, and I have turned his hill country into a wasteland and left his inheritance to the desert jackals.” ⁴Edom may say, “Though we have been crushed, we will rebuild the ruins.” But this is what the LORD Almighty says: “They may build, but I will demolish. They will be called the Wicked Land, a people always under the wrath of the LORD. ⁵You will see it with your own eyes and say, ‘Great is the LORD—even beyond the borders of Israel!’

Malachi was an early 5th-century prophet whose ministry focused on the priestly community in Israel after the rebuilding of the Jerusalem Temple and prior to the ministry of Ezra.¹ His mission was to rouse the remnant of Israel. They must not lose hope, and they must maintain covenant faithfulness.

Conditions were bleak. The small Jewish settlement was under the dominion of the vast Persian empire. The glorious kingdom prophecies of Haggai and Zechariah were a faint echo. The daily rituals of the Temple were tedious. Hostile tribal peoples surrounded them. It was time for a word from the Lord.

Malachi's audience was mixed. Some were faithful to God, some were apathetic, some were skeptical.² The book “... roughly follows the general pattern of prophetic literature, including an indictment (Mal 1:2-2:17...), the threat of divine judgement (Mal 3:1-5), instruction (Mal 3:6-12 ...) and the aftermath (Mal 3:13-4:3)...”³ Yet, its primary feature is six prophetic disputations.⁴ Hill explains:

¹ Dates vary only slightly. Victor Matthews gives it a date somewhere between 500 and 450 BC. Matthews, Victor H., *The Hebrew Prophets and Their Social World*, Baker Academic, Grand Rapids, MI, 2012, 194. John Walton expands the date to 515 BC due to the linguistic similarities of the book with 6th century Hebrew writings but gives it an end date of 458 BC to coincide with Ezra's reforms. Walton, John, *The NIV Cultural Backgrounds Study Bible*, “Oracles of the Prophets – Malachi,” Zondervan, Grand Rapids, MI, 2016, 1572.

² Andrew E. Hill notes that this mixed audience would receive the oracle in various ways, the faithful would see it as a word of encouragement, the apathetic would see it as a corrective to wrong thinking, the skeptical would perceive it as a threat of judgment. Hill, Andrew E. *The Anchor Bible Commentary*, “Malachi,” Doubleday, New York, NY, 1998, 162-163.

³ Boda, Mark J. and McConville, J. Gordon, editors, *Dictionary of the Old Testament Prophets*, “Malachi,” A.E. Hill, Intervarsity Press, Downers Grove, IL, 2012, 527.

⁴ The six are 1:2-5, 1:6-2:9, 2:10-16, 2:17-3:5, 3:6-12, 3:13-4:3.

The disputation speech pits the prophet against his audience in a type of “charge” versus “counter-charge” format featuring a declaration by the protagonist (the prophet Malachi), a refutation by the antagonist (the particular recipients of the oracle), and the emphatic rebuttal of the opponents’ polemic by the protagonist (Yahweh’s prophet).⁵

This paper focuses on the first of the six disputations in 1:2-5, the love of Yahweh. “I have loved you,” says the Lord. “But you ask, ‘How have you loved us?’” (1:2).

Keil and Delitzsch call these words “... the introduction and foundation of the whole book.”⁶ Schuller calls them “... the overarching framework... whatever will be said – accusation, judgment, promise – will come under this fundamental divine assertion.”⁷

Readers must approach this disputation of love through the lens of the covenant. Yes, it speaks of God’s love, yet love is about covenant faithfulness.

The thrust of Malachi’s preaching may be placed under the umbrella theme “covenant,” specifically the covenant of Jacob (i.e., the patriarchs (Mal 1:2), the covenant of Levi (Mal 2:4-5, an obscure reference, perhaps an allusion to the covenant made with Phinehas in Num 25:10-13), the covenant of marriage (Mal 2:14) and the covenant of Moses (Mal 4:4). The essential idea of covenant is that of an agreement or treaty that establishes a relationship between parties with attendant obligations and responsibilities. It is not surprising, then, that three of Malachi’s disputations deal with right relationships. The prophetic messenger also works on the premise that proper knowledge of God and his covenant is essential to maintain these right relationships.”⁸

What does “covenant” have to do with “love”? The Hebrew word for love, *ahab*, has a wide range of meaning. It may describe “human sexual love, emotion and affection, familial relationships, (and) norms for socio-ethical behavior....”⁹

William L. Moran has convincingly shown that extra-biblical texts used “love” to describe “... the loyalty and friendship joining independent kings, sovereign and vassal, king and subject.”¹⁰ It is a love that “...can be commanded. It is also a love intimately related to fear and reverence. Above all, it is a love which must be expressed in loyalty, in service, and in unqualified obedience to the demands of the law.”¹¹ Thus, the love-hate language of the OT and of Malachi should be viewed within the ancient environment of covenant loyalty.

Did it mean this for the people in Malachi’s time? While God did want a love relationship with his people that was intimate and heartfelt, it is unlikely that that was the focus in Malachi’s first words. The people were not sentimentally theorizing about love. The Jewish complaint could be stated: “If God is faithful to his covenant, where is the proof of his faithful covenant

⁵ Hill, 145.

⁶ Keil & Delitzsch, *Commentary on the Old Testament*, Vol 10, Minor Prophets, Grand Rapids, MI, Eerdmans, 1984, 430.

⁷ Schuller, Eileen M. *The New Interpreter’s Bible*, Vol VII, “Malachi,” Abingdon Press, Nashville, 1996, 854.

⁸ Boda and McConville, 530.

⁹ Hill, 146.

¹⁰ Moran, William L., “The Ancient Near Eastern Background of the Love of God in Deuteronomy,” *The Catholic Biblical Quarterly*, 1963, 77-87, p. 78.

¹¹ *Ibid.*, 78.

love? We see our struggle to survive amid an empire and satellite kingdoms that oppose our every move.” Schuller’s words help us understand the context in which these words were stated.

Many readers have the sense that with the book of Malachi the prophetic corpus per se and the OT as a whole end not with a bang, but with a whimper. The book does not belong to the time when Israel and Judah were political powers on the stage of the world empires, but comes from the post-exilic period, when Judah ... had been reduced to a minor administrative unit in the vast Persian Empire.¹²

Studies of settlement patterns and the size and material culture of sites in the early part of Persian rule do support the sense gleaned from the book of Malachi of a small and relatively poor community, without solid economic resources or great hopes, a community that could well ask, “Where is the God of justice?” (2:17 NRSV)...¹³

Where was the God of justice? How did God answer their complaint? He answered in verses 2-3. “Was not Esau Jacob’s brother?” ‘declares the Lord.’ “Yet I have loved Jacob, but Esau I have hated, and I have turned his hill country into a wasteland and left his inheritance to the desert jackals.”

It is noteworthy that God’s answer is not the standard “creation-exodus-land” pattern found in so many OT passages. Instead, the prophet reaches back to the patriarchal narrative of the brothers Esau and Jacob. In that story, one discovers that through Isaac’s blessing God entered a covenant relationship with Jacob who received the promises of a bountiful land while Isaac could only promise to Esau the lands to the southeast of Israel which featured small amounts of fertility and vast stretches of barrenness.¹⁴

But Malachi’s words were more than a reminder of what had happened over one thousand years before in patriarchal times. His words were meant to show the people what was unfolding before their eyes. Yes, God had judged Israel severely for its sin through the Babylonians, but he returned them to their land in faithfulness to the promises! They were in their ancestral lands! This was proof of God’s love. And the Edomites? Approximately 100 years prior in 552 BC, Nabonidus of Babylon had destroyed Edom. The people were scattered. Their civilization collapsed and was left to desert jackals.

The jackal would create revulsion for the Jews. It would remind the people of God’s warnings through Jeremiah that their land would become a haunt of jackals.¹⁵ “The jackal is both a wild and unclean animal according to priestly law and functions as a symbol of the desolation and defilement of Edom in a fashion similar to that of Isa 34:14; 35:7.”¹⁶ Despite efforts by some Edomites to rebuild, this never happened, and the inheritance of Esau was eventually overrun by the Nabateans.

¹² Schuller, 845-846.

¹³ Ibid., 848.

¹⁴ Hill, 154. “The territory of Edom was located on the southeastern rim of the Dead Sea and extended from the Brook Zered in the north to the Gulf of Aqaba in the south.... Egyptian records and archaeological evidence attest Edomite habitation of the area from ancient times (at least as early as the fifteenth century BCE...)”

¹⁵ See Jeremiah 9:11 and 10:22.

¹⁶ Hill, 155.

The exact date of Edom's collapse remains imprecise and the circumstances precipitating Edom's fall are uncertain.... By 312 BCE inscriptional evidence indicates that the Nabateans had overrun the region of Edom, making Petra their capital city. The remaining Edomites either migrated to Idumea or were absorbed by the Nabatean Arabs through intermarriage.¹⁷

Malachi 1:4 continues God's reply to Israel's complaint. "Edom may say, 'Though we have been crushed, we will rebuild the ruins.' But this is what the Lord Almighty says, 'They may build, but I will demolish. They will be called the Wicked Land, a people always under the wrath of the Lord.'"

The Wicked Land! The people under Yahweh's wrath! What could cause such epitaphs? The answer was obvious. One need only look at the enmity between the people and especially at what Edom did to Israel from the time Israel tried to traverse their land (Numbers 20:14-21) to the time when the Babylonians sacked Jerusalem, and the Edomites met fleeing Jews with cruelty (Obadiah 1:14).

Surprisingly, not everyone views it this way. Edith Schuller, while excellent in her comments on this passage in many respects, abandoned the historical situation and used this place in her commentary to advocate Calvinist-sovereignty-of-God arguments. She states:

We tend to think immediately in terms of moral causality and ask what Esau/Edom did so wrong as to merit this rejection. But this is precisely the connection that Malachi never makes. The rejection of Edom is not linked to any action or sin on its part....

If God's rejection of Esau is rooted in this inscrutable divine freedom, so too, by implication, is the choice of Jacob. The divine choice to love/choose Jacob is as great a mystery as the choice to love/hate Esau.¹⁸

Schuller's statements are surprising considering her scholarly grasp of Israel's history. Malachi did not need to enumerate Edom's sins. The people well knew the antagonism between the two brothers and nations. The memory of Edom's cruelty when the Jewish nation fell to Babylon was etched in its collective memory.¹⁹

Was Edom's historical calamity, therefore, based solely on the outworking of God's "inscrutable divine freedom"? Was its calamity at the hands of Nabonidus and its subsequent absorption by the Nabateans due to God's sovereign election to bless one and curse another? Certainly, that did play a part in the territory the descendants of Esau occupied and their destiny as a nation. But that could not be the only thing. If it were, what would have been the use of sending Malachi to tell Israel, once again, to repent? God used Edom as a warning for the covenant people of what life was like outside the covenant *because of sin*. Hill's comments are worth noting.

¹⁷ Ibid., 151.

¹⁸ Schuller, 856.

¹⁹ Most recently in the prophetic book of Obadiah.

The story of Esau is one of selfishness and disdain for the tokens of Yahweh's covenant (Gen 25:34). Edom came to personify this kind of profane self-centered existence. But the story of Jacob as Yahweh's choice to inherit the covenant of his fathers, despite his many faults and foibles, is one of great faith and obedience tempered by personal crisis.... The nation of Israel was supposed to personify this kind of 'pilgrim' faith and zealous worship, but instead was now in jeopardy of despising the very tokens of Yahweh's covenant even as Edom had done.²⁰

The laughter of jackals, the barrenness of hard rock. Jerusalem, like Edom, had once been a haunt of jackals. It had better wake up so that nothing like that would befall it again. Once more, Hill ably explains the atmosphere of that time.

The marked difference between the "loved" and "hated" of Yahweh extended even to their proverbial epithets: Edom became the "Territory of Evil" and "The People Cursed by Yahweh Perpetually," while postexilic Yehud is called "The Holy Land" (Zech 2:12) and "The Holy Mountain" (Zech 8:3). Israel had experienced the covenant love of Yahweh but sadly did not recognize it in the fall of Edom nor appreciate it as the handiwork of God. The postexilic community had become like their ancestors who forgot the deeds of God (Ps 78:7-8). By calling the people to consider a comparison of the historical experiences of Edom and Israel, Malachi seeks to jog the community's memory and awaken their collective consciousness to the reality of Yahweh's unfailing love (Ps 77:8, 10-12).

At this point, I can hear my Calvinist friends and brothers say, "Yes, Esau/Edom was responsible and was judged in history for its sin, but we must see that what came first was God's election for Paul says in Romans 9 that *before the twins were born and had done anything good or evil God made his choice*. God is using the historical situation with Edom as a paradigm for how he determines the salvation of one and not another."

Maybe. That will need to be resolved in a paper on Romans 9. This paper is about Malachi words in the environment and way of thinking in the fifth and sixth centuries before Christ. But when we understand this historical context, it will go a long way toward establishing a correct interpretation of Romans 9. For now, we must remain focused on Malachi.

Undoubtedly the people, especially the priests would know of the other oracles of Edom where its sins were cited as the cause of God's judgment.²¹ The point of Malachi's oracle was not to advocate predestinarian notions of individual salvation but to lift the hearts of those in Israel who were doubting God's love. They should not doubt his love. They were in a covenant with Yahweh. God had been with them in exile and had returned them to their land. But the land of Edom was devastated. All they needed was to walk about 50 miles southeast of Jerusalem and they would see that Edom, as a people were no more. Any attempts to rebuild would be forever rejected by God. And God concludes his words to the people by saying, "You will see it with your own eyes and say, 'Great is the Lord – even beyond the borders of Israel.'" But to see God's work, Israel must open its eyes, and if it does it will see that God loves his covenant people but

²⁰ Hill, 164.

²¹ See, for example, Amos 1:11-12 and Obadiah 1:10-14.

came to hate the nation of Jacob's twin brother, Esau. They must therefore continue to be faithful to him in response to his covenant faithfulness lest they once again suffer an Edom-like fate.

Thus, the love-hate language of Malachi 1:2-5 pertains to the destiny of the two peoples as nations. The patriarchal narrative does not say that God loved Jacob and hated Esau but only tells us that God entered a covenant relationship with Jacob and not with Esau through the double-blessing of Isaac their father who, the story tells us, loved Esau (Genesis 25:28)!

Malachi, speaking to his people, the descendants of Jacob, answered their complaint that God did not love them. He answers by pointing to the destiny of the nations. God kept his covenant with Jacob by restoring them to the land. God had no such promise to keep with Esau and because of his descendants' sin against the covenant people, God came to hate them and decreed destruction with no hope of national restoration. "You may attempt to rebuild but all efforts at nation building will be crushed," (Mal 1:4).

Thus, to use these words from Malachi to establish an abstract doctrine of double predestination is to ignore historical realities. Malachi was using the covenant history of Israel and Edom to warn his people in his time. Paul was doing the same. The people to whom belong the covenants and the promises (Rom 9:4) had missed their fulfillment and were in danger of losing them entirely if they did not repent (Rom 11:7-24). They would become like Edom, on the outside looking in.

But this is not the only word about Edom. We must now turn to Amos' words where we will discover something amazing about God and the Edomites. It seems that Isaac was not the only one who loved Esau and the Edomites!

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Amos 9:11-12 – Edom on the Inside!

“In that day “I will restore David’s fallen shelter—I will repair its broken walls and restore its ruins—and will rebuild it as it used to be, “so that they may possess the remnant of Edom and all the nations that bear my name,” declares the LORD, who will do these things.

Amos was an 8th-century prophet, the first of the writing prophets, but a man professionally trained in sheepherding²² and sycamore-fig farming²³ rather than in the schools of the prophets. His message was not favorable. God would bring judgment. He started well enough. The people must have delighted in his words when he spoke against Damascus of Syria (1:2-5), Philistia (1:6-8), Tyre of Phoenicia (1:9-10), Edom (1:11-12), Ammon (1:13-15), Moab (2:1-3), and Judah (2:4-5). But the joy was short-lived as his next words pierced the hearts of his audience “For three sins of Israel, even for four, I will not relent.”

Judgment was coming to Israel for forsaking the covenant and for social injustice. Because Amos is filled with the judgments of God, some scholars do not believe that he wrote the final two pericopes in 9:11-12 and 9:13-15 which offer hope and restoration. This paper will focus on the meaning of the first of these two visions of restoration, but first, are these scholars right when they say that the final words of this book were written by another? Gowan states,

Nothing in Amos 9:11 has any evident relationship with the rest of the book. Amos shows no interest in the division of the monarchy after Solomon’s death and says nothing of the state of the Davidic dynasty or of the fate of Jerusalem. Even the language referring to the ruin and rebuilding of the city is unusual for this book, but it is common in exilic materials (cf. Jer 31:4, 28). Verse 11 would be a meaningful promise in the middle of the sixth century BCE; it is hard to imagine how it could have seemed other than completely irrelevant to people of the northern kingdom 200 years earlier.”²⁴

Two points can be adduced to counter such statements. First, Biddle has demonstrated hints of repentance and hope throughout the book. The judgment oracles are addressed primarily to the political and priestly elite, not to the masses and are somewhat rhetorical. The words in 9:7-10 offer hope for a remnant.²⁵ Eidevall sees 9:7-10 as a “... transition from uncompromising judgment and total destruction ... to an emerging hope for restoration.”²⁶

²² John Walton notes that the Hebrew word for shepherd in 7:14 is different from the normal word for sheep breeding and refers to cattle herding. But both Hebrew terms were general, and it is best to think of Amos as working with a range of animals. Walton, John, *The NIV Cultural Backgrounds Study Bible*, Zondervan, 2016, Footnote on 1:1, 1479.

²³ Sycamore figs were not grown in Tekoa but in the western foothills and in the Jordan Valley. Walton speculates that he was either a migrant worker or an owner of fig orchards. The latter is to be preferred as it would be difficult to see a migrant worker also being a cattle/sheep breeder. *Ibid.*, 1479.

²⁴ Gowan, Donald E., *The New Interpreter’s Bible, Vol VII – Amos*, Abingdon Press, Nashville, 1996, 427.

²⁵ Biddle, Mark, “Sinners Only? Amos 9:8-10 and the Problem of Targeted Justice in Amos,” *Perspectives in Religious Studies*, Vol 43, No 2, Summer 2016, pp 161-175.

²⁶ Eidevall, Goran, *The Anchor Yale Bible, Vol 24 G – Amos*, Yale University Press, New Haven, 2017, 239.

Second, the restoration of David's fallen shelter would be relevant to Amos' audience. Eidevall says, "The view that the book of Amos as a whole expresses a pro-Judah and pro-Jerusalem perspective has gradually become more accepted."²⁷ He then quotes Davies who suggests that "the end of the book may not be, after all, an afterthought or a correction, contradicting the 'social' message of the remainder; rather, it may be precisely the culmination of the book's main theme: the supersession of Israelite sanctuaries by Jerusalem within the context of a broader supersession of Israel by Judah"²⁸ And we must not forget the words of the Chronicler who noted that many in the northern kingdom were sympathetic to Judah's cause and moved to the south (2 Chron 11:13-17).

Regardless of whether these were Amos' words or the words of a disciple or redactor, "Both oracles are addressed to a situation of loss, promising that the time will come when God will restore what has been lost and will transform the world to make it better than before."²⁹ What are these words of promise in Amos 9:11-12? First, God will restore the Davidic dynasty. Second, this restoration will have international implications.

The restoration of the dynasty is in 9:11 and consists of four phrases. God will restore David's fallen shelter, repair its broken walls, restore its ruins, and rebuild it as it used to be.

"Shelter" is from *מִטָּה*, a hut. Keil & Delitzsch contrast it with "house" (*בַּיִת*). The use of hut shows the "...degenerate condition of the royal house of David."³⁰ Kaiser takes "broken walls" to refer to the divided kingdom, "its ruins" to refer to David (because it is masculine singular and should be *his* ruins), and "rebuilding" as a reference back to the fallen hut because both are feminine.³¹ "Accordingly we note that the resurrecting of the dilapidated Davidic fortunes would involve a kingdom, a seed, and a dynasty."³²

Would this be relevant for the people of the north, especially during the time of Israel's prosperity under Jeroboam II? Gowan states that because Amos was Judean, he would naturally look forward to the "...reuniting of the monarchy, which had been divided after the death of Solomon. This would not be good news to the northern kingdom, so some suggest a continuing memory of Davidic glories in the north, in spite of Jeroboam's present superiority."³³ In addition, the "fallen" shelter could be translated as "falling" and refer not just to the division of the kingdom in 931 BC but to the ongoing "declining fortunes of the Davidic dynasty."³⁴

Douglas Stuart takes the rebuilding of the fallen hut (*sukkoth*) as a geographical location on the east side of the Jordan. This was

²⁷ Ibid., 267, Footnote 141.

²⁸ Ibid., 267, Footnote 141.

²⁹ Gowan, 426.

³⁰ Keil & Delitzsch, *Commentary on the Old Testament, Vol 10, Minor Prophets*, Grand Rapids, MI, Eerdmans, 330.

³¹ Kaiser Jr., Walter, "The Davidic Promise and the Inclusion of the Gentiles (Amos 9:9-15 and Acts 15:13-18); A Test Passage for Theological Systems," *JETS* 20 (1977) 97-111, 102.

³² Ibid., 102.

³³ Gowan, 426.

³⁴ Ibid., 426.

the staging area from which David subdued Israel's enemies... (and is) strongly associated with David's victories, including those over Edom (Ps 60:8-11 = 108:8-11). Its rebuilding would herald the return of Israel to power vis-à-vis its neighbors, in the restoration period prophesied by Amos. The issue here is not the rebuilding of Succoth per se but *David's Succoth*, as a metonymy for the kind of supremacy of God's reign through his people once enjoyed in Israel's past golden era.³⁵

Regardless of all that Amos and/or his followers/redactors had in mind, the current brokenness of the Davidic kingdom and his kingly line would be restored. God would rebuild it as it used to be. This is the message of 9:11 and Kaiser summarizes the hope clearly.

But it is important to notice also the phrase that completes this clause: "as it was in the days of old." Here is one of the keys to the passage, for it points back to the promise of 2 Sam 7:11, 12, 16 where God had promised that he would raise up David's seed after him and give him a throne and a dynasty that would endure forever.³⁶

When the restoration takes place, something else would happen which leads to Amos' words in verse 12; *the people would possess the remnant of Edom*.

Once again, Edom figures prominently in a prophetic oracle. Taken at face value and comparing it to other prophecies such as Isaiah 11:14, it seems clear that the restoration of David's house will bring victory over Edom and all the enemies of God's people. Gowan notes that "Peace seems to require victory over one's enemies as a prerequisite (cf. Lev 26:6-8; Isa 11:14-16; Zephaniah 2; Zechariah 9)."³⁷ This would be an especially pleasurable promise because of the atrocities that other nations inflicted upon Israel, particularly Edom.

But two curious things happened with this text. First, the LXX translators made two changes. First, עֲדוֹם, "Edom," was changed to אָדָם, "man or mankind," and שָׁרַף, to possess, was changed to שָׁרַף, to seek. Verse 12 now reads that the Davidic dynasty will be restored "so that *mankind* may *seek* (the Lord?) and all the nations that bear my name." Gowan speculates that "The very different meaning that the LXX gave to this verse represents Jewish thinking along these lines."³⁸ The changes leave the verb without an object, but he believes that "the Lord" may have been in the translator's mind. "If so, the version may reflect an interest in the eventual conversion of the Gentiles, which appears in some post-exilic Jewish literature."³⁹

This change may have been influenced by the final phrase, "and all the nations that bear my name." Was this a promise of military domination of the world or a promise of worldwide conversion?

"All the nations" looks back to the oracles of judgment against the nations in chapters 1 and 2.⁴⁰ But now, the emphasis is different. Just as God will reverse the misfortunes of the house

³⁵ Stuart, Douglas, *Word Biblical Commentary, Vol 31, Hosea-Jonah*, Word Publishers, Waco, TX, 1987, 397.

³⁶ Kaiser, 102.

³⁷ Gowan, 428.

³⁸ *Ibid.*, 428.

³⁹ *Ibid.*, 428.

⁴⁰ Eidevall, 239.

of David, he will also reverse the misfortunes of the nations because the phrase, “bearing my name,” indicates divine ownership. “The usage of this phrase in the OT always placed each of the objects so designated under divine ownership. What God or man named they owned and protected.”⁴¹ It would seem strange, then, to view this as a military victory; “I will defeat all the nations that bear my name.” One does not defeat what one owns. One repossesses what been taken captive or gone astray.

The second curiosity about this text is that the apostles and elders in Jerusalem followed the LXX version and used it as a biblical basis for the mission to the Gentiles.

¹³ When they finished, James spoke up. “Brothers,” he said, “listen to me. ¹⁴ Simon has described to us how God first intervened to choose a people for his name from the Gentiles. ¹⁵ The words of the prophets are in agreement with this, as it is written: ¹⁶ “‘After this I will return and rebuild David’s fallen tent. Its ruins I will rebuild, and I will restore it,¹⁷ that the rest of mankind may seek the Lord, even all the Gentiles who bear my name, says the Lord, who does these things’— ¹⁸ things known from long ago.

Thus, Amos, a prophet of judgment becomes a prophet of hope. The prophet of Judean superiority becomes the prophet of worldwide salvation, and Edom, the nation against whom more prophecies are uttered than any other becomes the symbol of humanity and God’s enterprise to restore the nations to himself by his grace!

Restoration blessing oracles do not usually predicate blessings on good behavior, in contrast to judgment oracles, which normally predicate punishment on a history of covenant disobedience.... Like the initial creation and blessing of Israel, its restoration blessings are wholly the product of Yahweh’s grace, requiring nothing but a willingness to turn again to him and to be obedient....⁴²

What would become true for Israel, its restoration, would become true for the world. Even Edom would one day no longer be on the outside looking in, but be on the inside, reconciled to his brother, Jacob! And the people whom God hated, because they were wicked toward the covenant people, would become the objects of his fatherly love, just as Father Isaac loved both his sons. Edom would be on the inside with his brother, Jacob!

⁴¹ Kaiser, 102.

⁴² Stuart, 397.

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